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Research Article

**ESMOLOL AND DEXMEDETOMIDINE FOR CONTROLLED
HYPOTENSION IN MIDDLE EAR SURGERIES - A
PROSPECTIVE, OPEN-LABELED, SINGLE-CENTER STUDY**¹Ali Nawaz, ²Dr Maryam Irshad, ³Dr. Alina Goheer¹Services Institute of Medical Sciences Lahore²Quaid-e-Azam Medical College, Bahawalpur, 2018³Quaid e Azam Medical College BWP**Article Received:** May 2020**Accepted:** June 2020**Published:** July 2020**Abstract:**

Objective and background- For providing the bloodless surgical field, blood transfusions and reduce the bleeding, controlled hypotension has been used. A central α -2 adrenergic, dexmedetomidine and cardioselective beta-blocker, esmolol can cause controlled hypotension. The main objective of this study is to analyze the effect of esmolol and compare it with dexmedetomidine for inhalation agent requirement, induction agent's dose requirements, controlled hypotension, middle ear surgeries and surgical field.

Methodology- This is a single center, open-labeled and prospective study. From Quaid-e-Azam medical College Bahawalpur, 100 patients of anesthesiologist's physical status were selected who were scheduled for the surgeries of middle ear. All the patients were divided into 2 group including 50, 50 patients randomly. One group received dexmedetomidine infusion and other received esmolol infusion.

Results- Both groups had the results which were comparable in surgical field assessment and hemodynamic parameters. In Group A which got dexmedetomidine infusion the requirement of thiopentone dose was 494 ± 12.93 mg whereas in group B who received esmolol infusion this requirement was 354.50 ± 17.26 mg. In Group A mean concentration of isoflurane was 13.79 ± 4.51 ml and in Group B it was 45.30 ± 5.85 ml. In Group A the requirement of vecuronium was 4.58 ± 0.46 mg whereas in Group B it was 11.19 ± 0.71 mg.

Conclusion- These drugs reduce the response of pressor equally, provide good surgical field and controlled hypotension. Moreover, the dose requirement of skeletal muscle relaxant, inhalation agent and induction agent can be reduced by dexmedetomidine.

Keywords: Middle ear surgery, dexmedetomidine, esmolol, controlled hypotension.

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INTRODUCTION:

For providing the bloodless surgical field, blood transfusions and reduce the bleeding, controlled hypotension has been used. A central α -2 adrenergic, dexmedetomidine and cardioselective beta-blocker, esmolol can cause controlled hypotension. For proper visualization under the microscope ear surgeries warrant a clear bloodless field. Esmolol is very useful in controlled hypotension and it can be titrated with its short duration of action. Likewise, dexmedetomidine reduce the bleeding in middle ear surgeries and provides controlled hypotension. Both of these drugs are comparable.

The main objective of this study is to analyze the effect of esmolol and compare it with dexmedetomidine for inhalation agent requirement, induction agent's dose requirements, controlled hypotension, middle ear surgeries and surgical field.

METHODOLOGY:

This study was conducted in Quaid-e-Azam Medical College, Bawalpur. This is a single center, open-labeled and prospective study. From Quaid-e-Azam medical College Bahawalpur, 100 patients of anesthesiologist's physical status were selected who were scheduled for the surgeries of middle ear. A written consent paper was signed from all the patients. Before induction of Anaesthesia, all patients received pentazocine 0.3 mg/kg, midazolam 0.03 mg/kg, ondansetron 0.08 mg/kg and glycopyrrolate 5mcg/kg. All the patients were divided into 2 group including 50, 50 patients randomly. One group received dexmedetomidine infusion and other received esmolol infusion. For 3 minutes with 100% oxygen preoxygenation was done. Before the end of the surgery this infusion was continued up to fifteen to twenty minutes.

Figure 1: Comparison of systolic blood pressure in the two groups

Figure 2: Comparison of systolic blood pressure in the two groups

As per the train for four ratio relaxants of skeletal muscle was observed. Finally, when surgery ends reversal with neostigmine 0.04 mg/kg and glycopyrrolate 10mcg/kg was done when eye opening and spontaneous respiratory attempts present. Systolic blood pressure and heart rate was continuously monitored during this operation. Likewise, intubation response and laryngoscopy were observed. The required amount of induction agent was noted. In every 30min TOF ratio was evaluated. To calculate the amount of isoflurane Dions formula was used. Using the assessment of surgical field score, the surgical field was assessed. The primary objective of this study is to compare the results of required inhalation agent, induction agent, surgical field and blood pressure for both drugs. Whereas as a secondary goal is to observe the side effects of these two drugs.

SPSS version 17 was used to analyze the results of this study. All means values were expressed in term of mean $\pm$ standard deviation.

RESULTS:

It was found that both of these group were comparable in terms of weight (Kg), sex (female/male), age (years). In group A mean blood pressure baseline was 124.12 ± 7.76 and in Group B it was 123.56 ± 6.81 . During induction mean heart rate was 78.24 ± 5.98 in Group A and it was 77.60 ± 5.74 in Group B. Also, during induction mean BP was 101.44 ± 3.25 and 101.32 ± 3.55 in Group A and B respectively. In Group A and B mean heart rate was 74.96 ± 4.73 and 75.04 ± 5.71 at 2 mins following intubation. Whereas during intubation mean BP was 94.88 ± 4.96 , 95.12 ± 5.17 in Group A and Group B respectively. Hence, between both two groups at induction, during and after intubation the mean HR and BP and mean baseline HR and BP did not show any statistical significance.

Table 1: Requirement of induction agent, inhalational agent and muscle relaxant in the twogroups

Requirement of	Study group		P value
	Esmolol	Dexmed	
Induction agent (mg)	494.00 ± 12.93	354.50 ± 17.26	0.022**
Inhalational agent (ml)	45.30 ± 5.85	13.79 ± 4.51	0.002**
Skeletal muscle relaxant (mg)	11.19 ± 0.71	4.58 ± 0.46	0.009**

Both groups had the results which were comparable in surgical field assessment and hemodynamic parameters. In Group A which got dexmedetomidine infusion the requirement of thiopentone dose was 494 ± 12.93 mg whereas in group B who received esmolol infusion this requirement was 354.50 ± 17.26 mg. In Group A mean concentration of isoflurane was 13.79 ± 4.51 ml and in Group B it was 45.30 ± 5.85 ml. In Group A the requirement of vecuronium was 4.58 ± 0.46 mg whereas in Group B it was 11.19 ± 0.71 mg.

DISCUSSION:

This is a single center, open-labeled and prospective study. For providing the bloodless surgical field, blood transfusions and reduce the bleeding, controlled hypotension has been used. A central α -2 adrenergic, dexmedetomidine and cardioselective beta-blocker, esmolol can cause controlled hypotension. For proper visualization under the microscope ear surgeries warrant a clear bloodless field. Esmolol is very useful in controlled hypotension and it can be titrated with its short duration of action. Likewise, dexmedetomidine reduce the bleeding in middle ear surgeries and provides controlled hypotension. Both of these drugs are comparable.

The primary objective of this study was to compare the results of required inhalation agent, induction agent, surgical field and blood pressure for both drugs. Whereas as a secondary goal was to observe the side effects of these two drugs.

Likewise, in the intraoperative period, the BP stayed at a lower level with a systolic BP somewhere in the range of 80 and 90mmHg. Thus, unmistakably esmolol and dexmedetomidine give controlled hypotension in center ear medical procedures of 2–3 h length. Nonetheless, the contrast between the two gatherings was factually not significant (Fig. 1 and 2). The consequences of this examination are steady with the outcomes acquired in another study. In present day sedative practice, we are utilizing an assortment of operators with various pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic profiles to augment their advantages and limit their

antagonistic impacts. Accordingly, it is alluring to utilize an adjuvant which would lessen the prerequisite of the sedative operators and along these lines diminish the resultant reactions. By diminishing the prerequisite of enlistment operator, inhalational specialist, skeletal muscle relaxant and narcotics, dexmedetomidine diminishes the complete portion of medications that the patient is exposed to and in this way diminishes the danger of portion related antagonistic impacts. In the current investigation, the thiopentone portion necessity and in Group A was 354.50 ± 17.26 mg with $P = 0.022$ and in Group B was 494 ± 12.93 which was measurably significant

Isoflurane has been seen as a decent specialist for ear medical procedures. We watched a huge decrease in isoflurane use in the dexmedetomidine bunch when contrasted with esmolol group. Dexmedetomidine produces a lessening in action of the projections of the locus coeruleus to the ventrolateral preoptic core.

CONCLUSION:

These drugs reduce the response of pressor equally, provide good surgical field and controlled hypotension. Moreover, the dose requirement of skeletal muscle relaxant, inhalation agent and induction agent can be reduced by dexmedetomidine.

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